

A Brief of My New Atomic Model Comparing With Universe

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Our new model for everything (before & after the ordinary matter particle formations) are able to explain of all kind of known & unknown fundamental particles & forces, such as neutrons, protons, electrons etc., including all hidden particles & forces, those are working in the background of ordinary matter elements, molecules etc. There created particle-likes formed tightly binding by Quark-likes with bosons of SU(6) provides biological molecules etc. through the process of structure formation by trapping nano-particles uses naturally created laser designated light rays made by photons & photon-likes quanta with exerted forces by the interactions between photon & neutrino-likes of new energies as explained in my previous articles.

This new model are based on Super Unified Theory of $SU(11) \supset SU(6) \times SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$, having a core nucleolus stage of energy within ordinary matter atoms which are gradually disappeared or evaporated with unfolding the required structure formation by ordinary matter atoms along with the appearance of some new kind of fundamental particle-likes in wave status maintaining the wave-wave duality of entanglement. Then found ordinary matter particle atoms with quantum entanglement of wave-particle duality. It is to be comparable with the formation of celestial bodies of galaxies between event horizon & particle horizon where remaining a black-hole at the centre region within event horizon, after then black-hole may gradually disappears or evaporated with unfolding matter bodies beyond the event horizon. A new kind of energy sources [as explained before in my articles] are found which are to be hidden in the background of all kind of lattice formation by ordinary matter elements, these are potentially so large that it fabricated any kind of structures by accumulating or synthesises matter particles for binding the lattice formation, such as the formations of single protein molecule to protein chains, then DNA through mRNA to DNA-strands or chain of DNA, then protein-protein interaction, DNA-protein interaction etc. We may assume that different kind of neutrino-like bosons of SU(6) must interact with photons of U(1), then appears photon-like quanta, although it is considering by scientists that free neutrinos of SU(2) does not interact with photons of U(1), similarly from all other neutrino-likes of the energy sources of SU(12), SU(24),.....etc. are interacted with photons within the electrons or electromagnetic ocean of our unfolding physical universe, created then fluxes of flows of incoming information through holographic optical rays then broadcasted through radio-designated energy waves called consciousness, which are actually responsible for the appearances of everything within our close body universe or close live-body systems. Hence found everything of this matter or physical universe after symmetry breaking of SU(11) & SU(5).

My new model having 'no' absolute empty spaces because I believe that any kind of empty spaces are always filled with some kind of new energies as explained before. In my explained theory of SU(11), we found there are two types of matter energies, unfolded with the symmetry breaking of the unified group SU(11) & then SU(5), which constructed the bodies of animates and inanimate. This two types of particles forming by quark-types but lepton-likes and quarks are tightly binding by the bosons of SU(6) and gluons of SU(3) simultaneously by changing of 30-number of bosons of SU(6) into 30-number of bosons of SU(5) or vice-versa by exchanging the bosons of SU(11) then by usual symmetry breaking of SU(5) with changing 6-bosons of SU(3) into 6-bosons of SU(2) or vice-versa by exchanging the bosons of SU(5). The strength of forces of SU(6) are always higher than the strength of force of SU(5) (comparing with vapour-liquid phase transition system that means like water vapour having latent heat of 540cal/g with same temperature of boiling water at 100°C), but the forces of SU(6) are seem to be remains hidden(as like latent heat) in the background when symmetry breaking of GUT of SU(5), ultimately we found macromolecular particles (like as releasing a large amount of latent heat, then vapour changes to liquid) where strength of strong forces of SU(3) increased gradually but strength of weak force of SU(2) decreases whereas strength of SU(6) remain unchanged (till it to be reaching like Big-Break singularity) as we advances towards the formations of macromolecules from the symmetry breaking of the unified groups of SUT & GUT. Thus, in the theory of SU(11), obviously possible to exchange the energies from the stages of SU(6) to SU(5), then excited for symmetry breaking of GUT of SU(5) by EHF(extremely high frequency) photon-like quanta, assuming as an incoming informational radio or laser designated light rays appearing like holographic optical tweezers (HOTs) for trapping nano-particles to the formations of macromolecules (as Bio-molecules) when lowering the frequency amplitudes with respect to the GUT matter particles. The incoming holography informational data with existing

data are subject to the memory of human or lives. Considering there always supplies non-monotonic new energies like laser pulses [it appeared as an exotic dancer, maintaining the seven rules of harmonium-rhythm of musical instruments], giving with sufficient intermediate time for the construction or deformation of sizes of matter element. Superposition of resonant vibration waves are considering for quantum dots or up-converting quantum masses, hence for constructions of different matter elements. We found there Brownian motion of colloidal fluids particles when trapping nano-particles by incoming laser designated beam of light rays with multiple foci carrying with information for the constructions of different animates & inanimate through synthesizing the elements or by chemical reactions for constructions of bio-molecules under hidden interactions forces creating a boundary with sensible close live-body of animates like as the close universe, otherwise we found only the compact matter elements of inanimate by GUT symmetry breaking of SU(5). Also, due to the non monotonic supplies of incoming information of new energies, we found different type of matter atoms like hydrogen, helium, lithium,.....etc. with increasing their atomic numbers, then found different heavy matter atoms. Then constructed different shape of structures through resonance of vibrations of elements, those are excited by the fluxes of photon-like energies to the inner & outer shell of subatomic stages of atoms called photoelectric effects etc.

Again, SU(6) encouraging for appearance of charges within ordinary matter atoms through different quark-likes for advancing towards the formation of complete close-body system through macromolecules. There created strong strengths current with massive fields by the bosons of SU(6) through the interaction between 15 pairs of W-type bosons particles & 5-nutrino-like Z-type bosons. These are therefore created charge particles then binding different quarks by gluons of SU(3), then found all kind of different material elements which are then formed heavy macromolecules by chemical reactions or synthesis as monomer then polymer etc. by the aforesaid hidden background interaction forces and ultimately found all kind of wanted and unwanted bio-molecules, like DNA's, single Protein etc. under the direct influences of SU(6) and indirectly by other forces of the energies of SU(12), SU(24),.....etc.

It was shown in my previous published articles that our physical or material universe goes through the stages where (10-7) flat universe, hence there is no adiabatic stage arises then closed with 5th & 6th dimensions and adiabatic stage arises through the appearance of micro-fluidic environmental situations, then DNH or multiple nano-holes or different shaped nano-aperture appeared for the trapping setup situation for biological improvements and we then characterized the ability to trap nano-particles against fluid flow by varying the flow rates. Comparing these with laboratory experiments, where showing that trapping can be achieved for 20 nm polystyrene particles (Thermo Scientific, Cat No. 3020A, Normal diameter 20 nm) for flow rates exceeding 10 ml/min at powers below 10 mW (corresponding to 0.5 mm/s flow velocities at the trapping surface). Then time evolution requires transmitted optical power through a double nano-hole for 10 mW of incident power, using 20 nm polystyrene spheres, while the solution flow-rate was increased in 0.5 mL/min increments after trapping (shown by the step at 825 seconds). Found, trapped nano-particle is released at a flow rate 12 mL/min while the measurements were repeated on different days by them with freshly made nano-sphere suspensions each time and the data was repeatable for all types of holes and all nano-spheres used. It was seen by them, that there is no evidence of heating effects in their experiments. Previously, trapped the protein BSA with similar laser intensities; and since that protein denatures irreversibly at 50uC and did not see such denaturing, thus believe that the heating is minimal and seen the dependence of the incident optical power and the flow-rate for which the trapped particle was released. The vertical error bars are standard deviations of the flow-rates for multiple trap and release events (greater than four events for each power). As an additional experiment conducted by them, by the green data point, first trapped a particle without flow and then reduced the power slowly until the particle was released. The horizontal error bar is the standard deviation of the power at which a trapped particle with high power has been released by decreasing the incident optical power without flow. With lower powers, the time to trap increases, as expected from the Arrhenius behaviour. For example, at 10 mW it took several hours to trap, and at 13.5 mW it takes 10 minutes. Then plotting the points, found a straight line is a linear fit of all the data which has a slope of 1 ml/(min³mW). So far, have not seen any departure from the linear behaviour, but this is limited by the laser intensity achievable.

The finite power is thus required to hold the particle in a stationary environment. This is because is a Brownian motion of the particle. For applications where the purpose is interaction of the trapped particles with other nano-particles, for example, to study protein-protein interactions, this flow capability is useful. Under the present conditions, they shown that was possible to deliver a secondary particle to the trapping site in about thirty

seconds, with a flow rate of 1.7 ml/min, which for a 20 nm trapped particle allows for stable trapping for powers of 3.5 mW and larger.

To explain the linear relation between the power and flow rate at which the particle is released, considering the interplay between the trapping force and Stokes' drag. The trapping force scales linearly with power. This is true for perturbative gradient force, but more generally true from Maxwell stress tensor (MST) analysis. The 'Stokes' drag force scales linearly with flow rate. Therefore, it is expected that the critical flow rate where flow overcomes the trapping force will scale linearly with power as well, as found in the experiments. The finite power is required to hold the particle in a stationary environment. This is because of the Brownian motion of the particle.

Thus, there created a micro-fluidic environment in the previous stages of matter universe then occurring normally optical trapping setup to trapping nano-particles against fluid flow. It was demonstrated in the experimentally setup laboratory that the flow-rate in which the trapped particle is released depends linearly on the incident optical power.

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